

Ottoman Poets Making Fun of the Zealot, the Sufi and, Exceptionally, Themselves

Zahit, Sufi ve İstisna Olarak Kendileriyle Alay Eden
Osmanlı Şairleri

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Abstract: Besides Ottoman satiric verses and facetiae (*hicv* and *hezl*) that were often harshly humorous and occasionally inmodest, a witty style of temperate nature was ubiquitous in poetry, especially in the genre *ğazel*. In fact, mild wit in the form of light mockery was a traditional characteristic of this poetry. Typified characters such as “the zealot” and “the Sufi” had pride of place as targets of this wit. On the other hand, the poets made fun of themselves only exceptionally. The aim of this study is to determine whether this *type*-bound humour, which was already very popular in the 16th century, continued to be popular until the begin of the literary influence of the West in the 19th century. For practical reasons, the poets and their humorous targets were restricted in this study. The poetry collections (*divāns*) of two poets each from the 16th and the 19th centuries were chosen to illustrate the development. The poets in question whose *divāns* were searched for samples of such wit are Me’ālî (d. 1535-36), Bâkî (d. 1600), Hızırğazâde Sa’îd (d. 1837), and ‘İffet of Bursa (d. 1840). The field of humour under study was restricted to the interaction of the poets with the zealot-*type* (*zâhid*) and the Sufi-*types* (*sûfî* and *sofû*). To this was added self-mockery in interplay with these conventionalized *types*. The fact that the zealot, the Sufi, and the *sofû* had evolved into *types* – though these *types* were not as strongly developed as, for example, the *types* of the Turkish shadow theatre – shows their traditional quality that heightened the probability of their continuing popularity. To sum up, this restricted search illustrates that this style of mild humour was still present in the first half of the 19th century. As to humorous self-deprecation by the poets, which was much rarer, we have seen that it could be light-hearted, as in Me’ālî’s poems on his physique in the 16th century, or serious, as in some poems of ‘İffet of Bursa in the 19th century. Such serious self-deprecation was presumably linked to mystic (*taşavvufî*) requirements regarding humility. What is intriguing in ‘İffet’s case is that both extreme humility and exaggerated self-praise are present, though not in the same poem.

Keywords: zealot, Sufi, antinomian, *sofû*, mockery.

Özet: Çoğu kez sertçe alaycı ve arada bir edepsiz olan Osmanlı manzum hiciv ve hezeli dışında ılımlı bir mizahi üslup, şiirde ve özellikle gazel türünde çok sık görülmüştür. Aslında hafif alay şeklindeki ılımlı mizah, bu şiirin geleneksel bir özelliği idi. “Zahit” ile “Sufi” gibi tiplendirilmiş karakterler, bu mizahın hedefi olarak en başta geliyordu. Diğer taraftan şairler ancak istisna olarak kendileriyle alay ediyordu. Bu çalışmanın amacı, on altıncı yüzyılda artık çok popülerleşmiş olan bu tür *tiplere* bağlı mizahın on dokuzuncu yüzyılda Batı’nın edebî etkisi başlayana kadar popüler olmaya devam edip etmediğini belirlemektir. Çalışmada şairler ve mizah hedefleri pratik nedenlerden dolayı kısıtlanmıştır. On altıncı ve on dokuzuncu yüzyıllardan ikişer şairin divanları gelişmeyi göstermek için seçilmiştir. Divanları bu tarz mizah örnekleri için taranan şairler Me’ālî (ö. 1535-36), Bâkî (ö. 1600), Hızırğazâde Sa’îd (ö. 1837) ve Bursalı ‘İffet’ir (ö. 1840). İrdelenen mizah alanı, şairlerin zahit, sufi ve sofû *tipleri* ile ilişkileriyle sınırlandırılmıştır. Gelenekselleşmiş *tiplerle* etkileşimde şairlerin kendileriyle alayı buna eklenmiştir. Zahit, sufi ve sofunun birer *tipe* dönüşmüş olması – bu *tipler* örneğin Karagöz gölge oyunundaki *tipler* kadar gelişmiş olmasa da – popülerliklerinin devamı ihtimalini arttıran geleneksel özelliklerini gösterir. Hasılı bu kısıtlı tarama, bu tür ılımlı mizahın on dokuzuncu yüzyılın ilk yarısında hâlâ görüldüğünü göstermektedir. Şairlerin, çok daha nadir olan kendilerini alaya almalarının ise on altıncı yüzyılda Me’ālî’nin kendi fiziğiyle alayı gibi neşeli ya da on dokuzuncu yüzyılda Bursalı ‘İffet’in bazı şairlerindeki gibi ciddi olabildiği görülmektedir. Kendini böyle ciddi aşığılama, muhtemelen alçakgönüllülük ile ilgili tasavvufi gereksinimlerle ilişkilidir. ‘İffet’in *Divân*’ında ilginç olan husus, hem had derecede tevazu hem de kendini aşırı övmenin bulunmasıdır; ne var ki bu iki özellik aynı şiirde görülmemektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: zahit, Sufi, rind, sofû, alay.

Ottoman satire and facetiae (*hicv* and *hezl*) in verse are composed in language that is often harshly satiric and either frankly or allusively immodest. However, the insults were not necessarily meant seriously.¹ At the same time, wit (*nükte*) that was of a temperate nature was ubiquitous in poetry, especially in the genre *ğazel*. In fact, mild wit dependent on various factors including mockery was a traditional characteristic of this poetry. The popularity of such wit is, of course, of sociolinguistic as well as of literary historical interest.

The present study² attempts to answer the question of whether this traditional characteristic continued to be popular until the begin of literary influence from the West in the 19th century. To this end, the poetry collections (*dīvāns*) of two moderately gifted poets of the 19th century, namely ‘İffet of Bursa (d. 1840)³ and Hızırâğazâde Sa’îd (d. 1837),⁴ were searched for samples of such wit. The reason middling poets rather than the best of the age were chosen is that they represent the average poet’s wit better, and we are looking for what is conventionally popular here. As a second step, these samples were compared with samples from the 16th century and, in this case, samples from the poetry of true masters of wit were chosen. This gave an idea of how the samples from the 19th century measure against those of the old masters. The reason for the choice of non-consecutive centuries was to allow enough time for societal dynamics to affect poetry (with poetry thereafter affecting societal dynamics in return). The two poets chosen for the 16th century are Bâkî (d. 1600),⁵ who has a fine sense

1 Edith Gülçin Ambros, “‘O Asinine, Vile Cur of a Fool Called Zâti!’: An Attempt to Show that Unabashed Language is Part and Parcel of An Ottoman ‘Idiom of Satire,’” *Journal of Turkish Studies=Türklük Bilgisi Araştırmaları* 27, no. 1 (2003): 109-117; *idem*, “On a Conventional Dimension of 16th Century Scurrilous Ottoman Satire: Keşfi’s (d. 945/1538-9) *Hicviyyât*,” *Journal of Turkish Studies=Türklük Bilgisi Araştırmaları*, special issue, “In Memoriam Şinasi Tekin I,” 31, no. 1 (2007): 21-39.

2 A preliminary paper on this study titled “On the Tradition of Ottoman Wit (*nükte*) of the Old School of Poetry, Arising from Wordplay, Unexpected Associations, and Self-deprecation” was read at the 25th Symposium of the Comité International des Études Pré-Ottomanes et Ottomanes held in Tirana, Albania on 21-25 June 2024.

3 *Bursalı İffet Dīvânı*, ed. Mehmet Arslan (Istanbul: Kitabevi, 2005).

4 Yasin Pekuz, “Hızır Ağazâde Sa’îd Bey Dīvânı” (Master’s thesis, Kırıkkale University, 2018).

5 *Bâkî Dīvânı: Tenkitli Basım*, ed. Sabahattin Küçük (Ankara: TDK, 1994).

of humour, and Me'ālī (d. 1535-36),⁶ who has an original talent of making fun of people in a candid but inoffensive way.⁷ As the field of wit is very large,⁸ the search for samples was restricted to wit featuring mockery of others and oneself. Finally, the topic of the samples was restricted to the ascetic zealot (*zāhid*) and the Sufi. For counterpoint, poems of self-mockery by Me'ālī and 'İffet were added. Most but not all the quoted excerpts are *ğazels* or couplets thereof.

1. *Types*

A sure sign of social and literary interaction is the crystallization in literature of *types* of people whose models are to be found in society. The zealot and the Sufi in Ottoman lyric poetry (*ğazeliyyāt*) are such *types*. These were familiar characters in the daily life of the Ottomans. The antinomian Sufi or the non-conformist person with Sufistic leanings (*rind*)⁹ were very much present, too. In addition to their real-life experience, the poets could form a second-hand opinion of such *types* by reading Persian poetry. The Persians had already integrated the zealot and the Sufi in their repertoire, highlighting some of their characteristics, and Persian literature had initial influence on Ottoman literature in many respects. In time and through repetition, the qualities and shortcomings possessed by or attributed to the zealot and the Sufi turned them into *types* with fixed associations and conventional figurative use. Unquestionably, such *types* were very practical for achieving a comical effect; however, they were not as exaggerated or perfect parodies as the *types* of the Turkish shadow theatre.

6 Edith Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes: The Lyrics of Me'ālī, An Ottoman Poet of the 16th Century* (Berlin: Klaus Schwarz Verlag, 1982).

7 His being inoffensive is true for his *ğazels* but not for other genres of poetry where he can be very offensive.

8 See, for example, Edith Gülçin Ambros, "Gülme, Güldürme ve Gülünç Düşürme Gereksinimlerinden Doğan Türler ve Osmanlı Edebiyatında İroni," *Nazımdan Nesire Edebî Türler*, eds. Hatice Aynur et al. (Istanbul: Turkuaz, 2009, 64-85; *Hicve Revâ, Mizaha Mâyil: Güldürücü Metinleri Anlamak*, eds. Hatice Aynur et al. (Istanbul: Klasik, 2018).

9 Being many-faceted, the term *rind* is almost impossible to define succinctly; see, for example, Mehmet Zeki Pakalın, "Rind," *Osmanlı Tarih Deyimleri ve Terimleri Sözlüğü* (Istanbul: Millî Eğitim Basımevi, 1983), 3:48-49. On antinomian Sufis see Ahmet T. Karamustafa, "Antinomian Sufis," *The Cambridge Companion to Sufism*, ed. Lloyd Ridgeon (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 115-124.

The popular habit of writing emulative poetry (*naẓīres*) made such *types* known to a larger audience and readership. A by-product of writing imitative poetry was an increased synchronic and diachronic “interaction” between poets. Networks of imitation can be very informative and inspiring; they can also further the conventional. In short, making fun of *types* was a stylistic trend.

2. Literary patrimony

The Ottoman poet mockingly criticized the zealot for his asceticism and dry religious overzeal. However, as already mentioned, reproaching the zealot was not an Ottoman invention, it was an attitude that was already present in older Persian poetry. For example, Ḥāfiẓ (d. ca. 1390) wrote in the 14th century:

*Slight me not, zealot, go thou hence ashamed,
For nought is slight that has by God been framed.*¹⁰

In Ottoman poetry, the ascetic zealot is frequently the butt of criticism and ridicule because he not only does not drink wine but constantly advises others to stop drinking. Of course, *mev*, the Persian word for “wine”, stands in Muslim mystical language for “strong love and its ardour”,¹¹ and so may either be the appellation of an alcoholic beverage or a metaphor for spiritual love. The ambiguity with the word *mev* is a traditional aspect that is characteristic of Ottoman lyric poetry. However, here is another line by Ḥāfiẓ that is not ambiguous at all.

Zealot, censure not the toper, guileless though thou keep thy soul;¹²

And here are two *rubāʿīs* ‘Omar Khayyām (d. 1132?) composed in the 11th or 12th century that are quite straightforward, too.

*Sweet is rose-ruddy wine in goblets gay,
And sweet are lute and harp and roundelay;
But for the zealot who ignores the cup,
'Tis sweet when he is twenty leagues away!*¹³

¹⁰ Herman Bicknell’s translation as quoted by Ainsworth R. Spofford, “Characteristics of Persian Poetry,” *The North American Review* 140, no. 341 (April 1885): 338.

¹¹ Ethem Cebecioğlu, *Tasavvuf Terimleri ve Deyimleri Sözlüğü* (Ankara: Rehber, 1997), 507.

¹² Herman Bicknell’s translation as quoted by Spofford, “Characteristics of Persian Poetry,” 336.

¹³ *Medieval Sourcebook: Omar Khayyam (d. 1123 CE): The Rubaiyat, c. 1120*, [trans. E.H. Whinfield], no. 85. Fordham University, <https://origin-rh.web.fordham.edu/halsall/basis/omarkhayyam-rub2.asp> (accessed 16 Feb. 2025).

And the second *rubā'ī*:

*Blame not the drunkards, you who wine eschew,
Had I but grace, I would abstain like you,
And mark me, vaunting zealot, you commit
A hundred fold worse sins than drunkards do.*¹⁴

3. The Ottoman poets

3.1. The 16th century

3.1.1. Me'ālī

Şūfī ("a mystic") is translated into English as "Sufi". However, *şūfī* is an ambiguous appellation in that it refers to two types of people. One of these is a person with a nonconforming free spirit, who has the approval of the poets, and the other is a person who adheres drily to the tenets of religion like the ascetic zealot, the *zāhid*, and is criticized by the poets. This ambiguity is removed when, instead of *şūfī*, the appellation *sofu*¹⁵ (in modern standard Turkish spelling) was used for the zealot-like "Sufi". In high-culture *Dīvān* poetry the spelling was always *ş-w-f-y* (generally transcribed as *şūfī* and occasionally as *şōfī* or *şofī*) and the reader had to decide in each instance whether a *şūfī* or a *sofu* was meant. For example, Me'ālī uses the word Sufi (*şūfī*) with both meanings, alternately criticizing the insincerity of the zealot-like Sufi and making fun of the propensity to drink of the nonconformist Sufi, as the following quotations show.¹⁶

In his elegy upon the death of his beloved cat, he probably speaks of the *sofu*, since he puts him on a par with the scandalmonger.

14 *Medieval Sourcebook: Omar Khayyam*, no. 11.

15 In common usage also *kaba sofū* ("rough *sofu*").

16 The transcription of all the quotations in this study is as in the original publications. All translations are my own unless otherwise noted.

Me'ālī, ¹⁷ no. ¹⁸ 11/XIII (*murabba*¹⁹), *fe' ilātün (fā' ilātün) - fe' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilün (fā' lün)*

Değme güyendede yoğ-idi anuñ avāzı

Zühre işitse şadāsın birağurdı sāzı

Hıç sevmezdi ne şüfiyi ve ne ğammāzı

*Nedelüm āh pisi neyleyelüm vāh pisi*²⁰

Not every singer had a voice like his...

Venus would stop playing the lute should she hear his voice!

He could stand neither the scandalmonger nor the Sufi!

Alas what can we do, pussy! What can we do, ah pussy!²¹

The poets of the old school of poetry liked plays on words and Me'ālī was no exception. He had been kadi of Sofia (among other locations) and obviously could not pass over the chance to quip “Paradise for the Sufi, the city of Sofia for me!” (*Cenneti şüfiye ve Şöfiya şehrini baña*²²).

In the following couplet, Me'ālī implies that the Sufi tries to stop drinking, swearing that he will drink no more, but cannot remain abstinent.

Me'ālī, no. 46/4 (*ğazel*), *mef' ülü - mefā' ilü - mefā' ilü - fe' ülün*

Şüfi baña eydür ki şarāb içmege and iç

*And içmezem anuñ gibi yalan yere va-llā*²³

The Sufi says to me, “Swear not to drink wine.”

By God, I don't perjure myself like he does!²⁴

Elsewhere, Me'ālī openly accuses the Sufi of a passion for drinking wine (*mey*). Clearly, the term “wine” is not used in a metaphorical sense here.

¹⁷ The verses by Me'ālī that are quoted in this study were previously published by Ambros in *Candid Penstrokes*.

¹⁸ The poems in this edition are enumerated without regard to genre and form.

¹⁹ A form of poem in stanzas of four hemistichs each.

²⁰ Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 178.

²¹ Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 37.

²² Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 169. This is the first hemistich of 9/II (a *murabba*'), metre: *fe' ilātün (fā' ilātün) - fe' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilün (fā' lün)*.

²³ Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 222.

²⁴ Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 102.

Me'âlî, no. 114/3 (ğazel), *mef'ülü - mefâ'ilü - mefâ'ilü - fe'ülün*
Şol resm-ile oldı mey-i cân-pervere 'aşık
*Kim şüfi tahâret şuyını meyden edindi*²⁵

The Sufi conceived such a passion for soul-nourishing wine
 That he used wine in place of water for his ablutions!²⁶

Me'âlî, no. 98/5 (ğazel), *mefâ'ilün - mefâ'ilün - fe'ülün*
Me'âlî mescide varurđ şüfi
*Dem-â-dem mest [ü] evgâr olmayadı*²⁷

Me'âlî, the Sufi would come to the mosque
 If he weren't drunk and tight time and again!²⁸

Me'âlî, no. 146/1 (ğazel), *mef'ülü - fâ'ilätü - mefâ'ilü - fâ'ilün*
Mey-hânede var-idi bugün gâyet izdihâm
*Tâcına koydı şüfi meyi bulımadı cân*²⁹

Much crowding and pressing went on in the tavern today.
 The Sufi put the wine in his cap [for] he couldn't find a cup!³⁰

There is no ambiguity whatever in Me'âlî's mockery of the zealot (*zâhid*)
 whom he accuses of insincerity regarding asceticism.

Me'âlî, no. 192/4 (ğazel), *fâ'ilätün - fâ'ilätün - fâ'ilätün - fâ'ilün*
Münharif olmuş yübüsetden mizâcuñ zâhidâ
*Bir iki ayak şulu meyle seni hoş edeyin*³¹

You're out of sorts from being parched, O zealot.
 Let me make you happy with one or two cups of watered wine.³²

Me'âlî, no. 130/3 (ğazel), *fâ'ilätün - fâ'ilätün - fâ'ilätün - fâ'ilün*
İhtirâz êdüğine mahbûb-ile meyden sebeb
*Zâhidün takvâsı şanmañ hissetidür hisseti*³³

25 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 290.

26 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 102.

27 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 274.

28 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 103.

29 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 146.

30 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 103.

31 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 370.

32 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 104.

33 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 306.

Don't think the reason the zealot shuns lovable boys and wine
Is his pious fear of God. It is his avarice! His avarice!³⁴

3.1.2. Bākī

Bākī is a master of double entendre, as seen in his following “treatment” of the zealot:

Bākī, *gazel* 307/5, *fe' ilātün (fā' ilātün) - fe' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fa' lün*
Zāhid ol şiklet ile uçmağa hāzır lanma
*Çıkar ol cübbe vü destārı biraz hıffet bul*³⁵

Şiklet means “weight” or “gravity” and *hıffet* means “lightness” or “frivolity”. And the word *uçmak* can be the substantive “paradise” or the verb “to fly”. So, we can translate this couplet in two ways. Either as

Zealot, don't get ready for *heaven* with such gravity.
Take off that robe and turban and acquire a little frivolity.

Or alternatively, conjuring up the image of a stout zealot getting ready to fly:

Zealot, don't get ready *to fly* with that weight.
Take off that robe and turban and become a little lighter!³⁶

A mock-heroic verse:

Bākī, *gazel* 460/3, *fā' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilün (fa' lün)*
Gül gibi bāde-i rengine ne ibrām gerek
*Zāhidün kanın içerdüm eger ibrām olsa*³⁷

What need is there to force rose-colored wine on one?
When forced, I'd drink the blood of the zealot!

Bākī's opinion of the zealot's mental capacities is decidedly low.

³⁴ Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 104.

³⁵ *Bākī Dīvānı*, 289.

³⁶ Prior publication of this dual interpretation by Edith Gülçin Ambros, “Linguistic Duality and Humour as a Stylistic Marker in Ottoman Lyric Poetry of the 16th Century,” *Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde des Morgenlandes*, special issue, “Orientalische Landschaften,” no. 100 (2010): 55.

³⁷ *Bākī Dīvānı*, 385.

Bākī, *gazel* 277/7, *fā' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilün*
Şi'r-i Bākīye kulak tutmasa zāhid ne 'aceb
*Söz güherdür ne bilir kadrini nā-dān güherün*³⁸

It's no wonder the zealot won't listen to Bākī's poems.
 Words are gems. How should the ignorant know the worth of gems!

Bākī, *gazel* 446/1, *mef' ilü - fā' ilātü - mefā' ilü - fā' ilün*
Der-gāh-ı Hākka derd ile 'āşık niyāzda
*Bātıl taşavvur itmede zāhid namāzda*³⁹

The lover is entreating the Court of God in pain.
 The zealot is imagining falsehoods at prayer.

A double-barrelled insult aimed at the lover's rival and the *sofu*; he is actually calling them both "donkey!". Please note that the lover is mostly to be identified as the poet himself.

Bākī, *gazel* 422/4, *fā' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilün (fā' lün)*
*Yār ışığında rakībün yirin umma şöfi*⁴⁰
*Bağlamaz kimse seni ol kapuda har yirine*⁴¹

Don't hope for the rival's place at the beloved's threshold, Sufi.
 Noone will tie you at that door in place of a donkey.

The following is about the nonconformist, drinking, singing, dancing mystic, that is the *şüfi*, not the *sofu*.

Bākī, *gazel* 82/2, *mefā' ilün - mefā' ilün - mefā' ilün - mefā' ilün*
Güzeller şevkine şohbetde şöfi çalgusuz oynar
*Veli her bilmeyen eyle şanur anı semā' eyler*⁴²

In the heat of the fair ones' company, the Sufi dances without instrumental music,
 Yet everyone who isn't in the know thinks he is whirling as a dervish.

The whole following poem reflects Bākī's *carpe diem* attitude.

38 *Bākī Dīvānı*, 271.

39 *Bākī Dīvānı*, 376.

40 In this edition, *şüfi* is written as *şöfi*.

41 *Bākī Dīvānı*, 362.

42 *Bākī Dīvānı*, 151.

Bākī, *ğazel* 181, *mefā'ülün - mefā'ülün - mefā'ülün - mefā'ülün*

- 1 *Bahār eyyāmı geldi taze 'aşıklık zamānidur*
Sular cüş itdügi demdür bulanıklık zamānidur
- 2 *Çemende şu gibi şöfi şarāb içmek gerek şimdi*
Behey şöfi bu mevsimler ne ayıklık zamānidur
- 3 *Müdām içen münāfikdur dimiş minberde bir vā'iz*
Ne çāre hey Müselmānlar münāfiklik zamānidur
- 4 *Açılsun gönümüz sāki kadeh şun var ise bākī*
Temāşā eyle āfāki çü açıklık zamānidur
- 5 *Senün nazm-ı ciger-süzün tutupdur dehri ey Bākī*
Gözün açsun kamu şā'ir uyanıklık zamānidur⁴³
- 1 The Spring days have come; it's the time for fresh loving.
It's the moment when streams overflow, the time they are turbid.⁴⁴
- 2 Sufi! In the meadow now, one should drink wine like water.
Hey Sufi! What a time for being sober these seasons are!!⁴⁵
- 3 A preacher said at the pulpit, "He who drinks wine⁴⁶ is a hypocrite!"
What can one do? Hey Muslims, it's the time of hypocrisy!
- 4 Let our hearts rejoice, cupbearer! Offer a cup if there is some [wine] left.
Look at the horizons for it's the time of open spaces.
- 5 O Bākī! Your heart-scorching poetry has conquered the world.
Let all poets wake up! It's the time for being wide awake!

43 *Bākī Dīvānı*, 212.

44 Turbid streams and brooks in spring are a familiar picture in *Dīvān* poetry.

45 Bākī obviously implies the opposite, i.e., "for not being sober".

46 The word for wine here, *müdām*, also means "always", so we have the alternate interpretation "He who drinks always".

3.2. The 19th century

3.2.1. Hızırâgazâde Sa'îd

Hızırâgazâde Sa'îd was said to be witty (*nüktedân*) though not interested in putting his wit into writing.⁴⁷ The result is that we found little to quote from him in this context. He is mainly included as a contrast to his much more productive contemporary 'İffet of Bursa.

Sa'îd, no.⁴⁸ 25/4 (*ğazel*), *fe' ilâtün (fâ' ilâtün) - fe' ilâtün - fe' ilâtün - fe' ilün (fa' lün)*
Bâde içdimse güzel sevdim ise ey zâhid
*Neyledim ben saña bu mertebe ta'zîre göre*⁴⁹

What if I drank wine, loved the Fair, O zealot?
 What did I do to you to be chastised so?

Ramadan, the month of fasting called *rûze-i ğam* "the fast of sorrow" below, is followed by the month *Shawwâl*. The poet gives a frivolous reason for having drunk wine during Ramadan, saying he thought the month *Shawwâl* had already begun – an invalid excuse, of course, since the prohibition to drink wine is not restricted to Ramadan.

Sa'îd, no. 23/4 (*ğazel*), *mefâ' ilün - mefâ' ilün - mefâ' ilün - mefâ' ilün*
*Amân 'aff'eyle*⁵⁰ *mey içdimse zâhid rûze-i ğamda*
*Hilâl-i ebrû-yı sâkîyi meh-i şevvâl şandım ben*⁵¹

Mercy! Forgive me, zealot, for drinking wine during the Fast of Sorrow.
 I mistook the crescent of the cupbearer's eyebrow for the moon of [the month] Shawwal!

The following couplet is out of a poem that is exceptionally not composed according to Arabo-Persian prosody ('*arûż*) but according to syllabic prosody (*hece vezni*). In this case, there are 14 syllables to a line.

⁴⁷ See Kadriye Kocaoğlu-Kocagöz, "XVII. Yüzyıla Ait Bir Tabir: 'Kat Kat Helâl Olsun' Üzerine," *Osmanlı Edebî Metinlerinin Anlam Dünyası Sempozyumu, 12-13 Mayıs 2017, Bilecik: Bildiriler Kitabı/Proceedings Book*, ed. Mehmet Özdemir (Bilecik: Bilecik Şeyh Edebali Üniversitesi Yayınları, 2019), 233.

⁴⁸ The poems in this edition are enumerated without regard to genre and form.

⁴⁹ Pekuz, "Hızır Agazâde Sa'îd Bey Dîvânı," 155.

⁵⁰ Transcribed thus in Pekuz, "Hızır Agazâde Sa'îd Bey Dîvânı," 153.

⁵¹ Pekuz, "Hızır Agazâde Sa'îd Bey Dîvânı," 153.

Sa'îd, no. 31/3 (syllabic metre)
Nîgeh[-i] mestîñ için zâhid bî-neş'e eyle
*Dâhîl-i meclis olur fâsık-ı maħrûm gibi*⁵²

The zealot is so joyless because of your drunken glances.
 He is entering the assembly like a disappointed sinner.

The following is an example of the construction called “complement of an ancient hemistich” (*taẓmîn-i mışra‘-ı ‘atîk*), in which the complement precedes the older hemistich. Whereas the older hemistich is noncommittal, the new hemistich by Hızırğazâde Sa'îd intimates the Sufi's propensity to drink.

Sa'îd, no. 66 (*müfred*, “independent couplet”), *mefâ‘ilün - mefâ‘ilün - mefâ‘ilün - mefâ‘ilün*
Mey içdi ba‘d el-iftâr etmeden teklîf şüfîye
*O katmer baklava benden yaña*⁵³ *kat kat helâl olsun*⁵⁴

He drank wine after breaking fast without offering some to the Sufi.
 May that flaky baklava be my offer with all my blessing!

3.2.2. ‘İffet of Bursa

Compared to Hızırğazâde Sa'îd, ‘İffet of Bursa is a more original and productive poet in this regard, as the following examples show.

‘İffet, *müfred* 11, *mef‘ülü - mefâ‘ilü - mefâ‘ilü - fe‘ülün*
Zâhid baña sen çeşm-i haķâretle bakarsın
 ‘İffet n’ola şâ‘ir ise kâfir de degül ya⁵⁵

Zealot, you look at me with insulting eyes.
 What if İffet is a poet? After all, he is not an unbeliever!

An independent couplet that obviously is about the *sofu*:

52 Pekuz, “Hızır Agazâde Sa'îd Bey Dîvânı,” 162.

53 In the edition: *baña*; corrected as the original attributed to the Ottoman poet Sâbit of Bosnia (d. 1712) has *yaña* and not *baña*; cf. Kocaođlu-Kocagöz, “XVII. Yüzyıla Ait Bir Tabir,” 232; and *Tayyâr-zâde Atâ: Osmanlı Saray Tarihi: Târîh-i Enderûn*, ed. Mehmet Arslan (Istanbul: Kitabevi, 2010), 4:390.

54 Pekuz, “Hızır Agazâde Sa'îd Bey Dîvânı,” 186.

55 *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 124.

'İffet, *müfred* 3, *fe'îlâtün (fâ'îlâtün) - fe'îlâtün - fe'îlâtün - fe'îlün (fa'lün)*
Şûfiyânun nesi var dâm u riyâdan ğayri
*Rîş ü destâr ile tesbîh ü 'aşâdan ğayri*⁵⁶

What do the *sofus* have other than deceit and hypocrisy,
 Other than a beard and a turban, a rosary and a staff?

The following dervishes are apparently *sofus* with a materialistic streak.

'İffet, *ġazel* 47/4, *meġâ'ilün - meġâ'ilün - meġâ'ilün - meġâ'ilün*
Eġer dest-i kâderden kem-ter olsa bir gice nâmun
*Velev kuġb-ı cihân ol tekyede bir derviġün kalmaz*⁵⁷

Should your bread from the hand of fate happen to be less one night,
 Not one dervish would remain in the convent even if you were the pole of the universe.

In the following couplets, 'İffet makes fun of the dry-natured *sofu*.

'İffet *ġazel* 122/1, 4, *meġâ'ilün - meġâ'ilün - meġâ'ilün - meġâ'ilün*

1 *Ne çâre almamıġ 'aşk u mahabbetden şafâ şûfi*
Özin fark itmeyüp zâhirlle olmuġ mübtelâ şûfi

4 *Edâ-yı şükriñ it cennetle ġûyâ kim mübeġġersin*
*Eġer bir nîm tebessümle iderse merhabâ şûfi*⁵⁸

1 The *sofu* did not find delight in love and affection...what can one do?
 He did not realize his inner self and became addicted to the external.

4 Should the *sofu* say "Welcome!" with but half a smile,
 Offer thanks as if given the joyful news of having a place in paradise.

4. Self-mockery and self-deprecation⁵⁹

This concerns 'İffet of Bursa especially and, as far as bantering self-mockery goes, Me'âlî. It is less relevant for Bâķî and Hızırâġazâde Sa'îd. Therefore, we shall restrict ourselves to making a few remarks about Me'âlî before passing on to 'İffet of Bursa.

⁵⁶ *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 123.

⁵⁷ *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 62.

⁵⁸ *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 103.

⁵⁹ Cf. Tolġa Öntürk, "Klasik Türk Edebiyatında Mizahın Farklı Bir Yönü: Şairin Kendini Alaya Alması," *Uluslararası Türk Dili ve Edebiyatı Araġtırmaları Dergisi*, no. 4 (April 2021): 35-42.

4.1. Me'ālī

Me'ālī made fun of himself in some of his *kıt'as* and *müfreds*, that is in verse types that have a larger spectrum of themes than the *ğazel*. We have already mentioned that Me'ālī was a judge (*kadi*), let us add that he was unable to grow a beard or moustaches, that is, he was *köse*.

Me'ālī, no. 379 (*müfred*), *mefā'ilün - mefā'ilün - fe'ülün*
Me'ālīyi görüp dedi karılar
*Abu bizden daħi kâzî olurmuş*⁶⁰

The women saw Me'ālī and said,
 “Hey look at that! Even one of us can become a *kadi*!”⁶¹

Occasionally, he also laughed at himself in his *ğazels*. For example:

Me'ālī, no. 183/5 (*ğazel*), *fā'ilātün - fe'ilātün - fa'lün*
Mevsim-i gülde Me'ālī meye and içmişiz
*Bir delü şüfî bir anuñ şînarı kevden sen*⁶²

In the season of the rose, Me'ālī, you [two] have sworn off wine...
 A crazy Sufi and you, fool, of a like mind!⁶³

4.2. 'İffet of Bursa

In contrast to Me'ālī's lightheartedly poking fun at himself in the 16th century, Bursalı 'İffet's 19th-century *Dīvān* contains remarkable *ğazels* with severe self-deprecation. Furthermore, 'İffet alternately proclaims extreme humility and blatant over-confidence coupled with utter self-satisfaction. However, he does not combine humility and arrogance in one and the same *ğazel*. The occurrence of both traits in such forcefulness in the *Dīvān* of one poet is exceptional as far as we know.

The following *ğazel* is an example of severe self-deprecation. It is also remarkable because of structural particularities: a long “refrain” (*redif*) as part of the end-rhyme; inner rhyme (*musammat*), and the novelty of the pen name (*maħlaş*) in every couplet.

60 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 501.

61 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 15.

62 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 361.

63 Ambros, *Candid Penstrokes*, 106.

'İffet, ğazel 92, müstef'ilün - müstef'ilün - müstef'ilün - müstef'ilün

- 1 *Mecnûna hâkim ne'ylesün ta'lîm-i 'âlim ne'ylesün*
Karnında yok cim ne'ylesün 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesün
 - 2 *Bir bî-kes ü bî-çâresin bir 'âciz ü âvâresin*
Bilmem kime yalvarasın 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesin
 - 3 *Bir boş gezenler başısın el la'l ise sen aşısın*
Ne sûhte ne biñbaşısın 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesin
 - 4 *Hüsni-i melâhat sende yok şavr u kıyâfet sende yok*
Halka ziyâfet sende yok 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesün
 - 5 *Bezmün enîs-i mey degül destün sezâ-yı ney degül*
'Âlemdede hiç bir şey degül 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesün
 - 6 *Şad rîş ü destâruñ mı var bir reşk olur kâruñ mı var*
Bir yâr-ı ğam-b'âruñ mı var 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesün
 - 7 *Manîk bilür nâtik mısın akrânuña fâ'ik misin*
Bir mesnede lâyık mısın 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesün
 - 8 *Bir nesneye irmez elün bu hâl ile tırmaz dilün*
Çâh-ı 'acebdır menziliñ 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesün
 - 9 *Sen şabr idüp hoş-hâtır ol lutf-ı Hudâ'ya hâzır ol*
Koy halkı Haşk'a nâzır ol 'İffet seni kim ne'ylesün'⁶⁴
- 1 What is the judge to do with the crazy? What is the scholars' teaching to do?
He is an ignoramus, what is he to do? İffet, what is anyone to do with you?
 - 2 You are without a friend and without help, you are a failure and desolate.
I don't know with whom you should plead. İffet, what is anyone to do with you?
 - 3 You are the head of idle roamers. If the others are rubies, you are amber.
You are neither a student nor a major. İffet, what is anyone to do with you?
 - 4 You lack the grace of being pleasing, you lack polished manners and fine clothes.
You don't give banquets for the folk. İffet, what is anyone to do with you?
 - 5 Your feast is unfamiliar with wine; your hand is unfit for the flute.
Good for nothing in this world! İffet, what is anyone to do with you?

64 *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 86.

- 6 Do you have a hundred fineries and turbans? Do you have work that is the object of envy?
Do you have a gloomy darling? İffet, what is anyone to do with you?
- 7 Are you a speaker who knows logic? Are you superior to your peers?
Are you worthy of a post? İffet, what is anyone to do with you?
- 8 You are capable of nothing. You keep talking in this condition.
Your station is the pit of wonder. İffet, what is anyone to do with you?
- 9 Be patient and of good cheer. Be ready for the grace of God.
Leave the people alone! Look on God! İffet, what is anyone to do with you?

However, in another *ğazel* 'İffet shows a combative spirit in defending himself:

'İffet, *ğazel* 25, *fe' ilātün (fā' ilātün) - fe' ilātün - fe' ilātün - fe' ilün (fa' lün)*

The poet's pen name (*maḥlas*) is exceptionally in the first instead of in the last or the penultimate couplet.

- 1 *Kiminiñ şahñ-ı każâsı kiminiñ hâkimi var*
Ben de bilmem bu ğarîb 'İffet' üñ âyâ kimi var
- 2 *N'ola fehñ itmez ise rütbe-i isti' dâdım*
Felegün ol kadar âyîne-i idrâki mi var
- 3 *Neyle tutsun dehen-i vâ'izi şûrîde-mizâc*
Hân-ı imsâki mi var sübha vü misvâki mi var
- 4 *İmtizâc itmedi bu halk ile bilmem ki dilün*
Bir zemîn-i diğeri başka bir eflâki mi var
- 5 *Bir nigâh ile ider 'âlemi ser-mest ü harâb*
Kimseden ğamze-i hûnîñüñ 'aceb bâki mi var
- 6 *Böyle bî-kaydsın ammâ geliyor mâh-ı şıyâm*
*Hâzır olmuş şeker ü kahve vü tönbâki mi var*⁶⁵

- 1 Some have a judgeship, some have a judge,
And I don't know whom this poor İffet might possibly have.
- 2 What if fate doesn't understand the degree of my aptitude,
Does it have that much vision of comprehension?
- 3 With what can the fool make the preacher stop blabbing?
Has he got food to eat before the fast? Has he got a rosary and a toothbrush?

- 4 Your heart did not get on well with these people, I wonder why.
Does it have another world, a different sky?

[Now he speaks of the beloved:]

- 5 With one look, he makes everyone drunk and madly in love.
Are the cruel coquettish glances afraid of anyone?

[And now he addresses himself and ends the poem on a hilarious domestic note:]

- 6 You are without a care like that, but the month of Ramadan is coming.
Is there any sugar and coffee and tobacco of Shiraz made ready?

He combines a nonconformist attitude with an ironic sense of humour.

‘İffet, *ğazel* 39/4, *fâ‘ilātün - fe‘ilātün - fe‘ilātün - fe‘ilün (fa‘lün)*
Ṭavrımız meşreb-i gerdûna muğâyirdir hep
*Rızķımız hâle-şifat zenbil ile gökden iner*⁶⁶

Our manner is always contrary to fortune’s nature.
Our daily bread descends halo-like in a basket from the sky.

In the next poem ‘İffet expresses extreme self-deprecation (*tezellül*). There is no humour here, but there is a philosophical streak.

‘İffet, *kıṭ‘a* (a type of short poem) 2, *fe‘ilātün (fâ‘ilātün) - fe‘ilātün - fe‘ilātün - fe‘ilün*

- 1 *Bu kadar ni‘mete bir vechile şâyân degülüz*
Cehlimizden hele şermende-i ihsân degülüz

- 2 *Bilmeyiz zâtımızuñ mazhar-ı zât oldıgım*
*Gerçi kim hey‘et-i insândayız insân degülüz*⁶⁷

- 1 We⁶⁸ are not worthy in any way of so many benefactions.
Out of ignorance we don’t even blush with shame at the beneficence.
- 2 We don’t know that our person is a manifestation of essence.
Though we are in the form of human beings, we are not human beings.

Such a high degree of self-deprecation brings up the question of whether there is more to this than just exaggerated modesty or humility. As a matter

66 *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 57.

67 *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 121.

68 The plural here is probably pluralis modestiae.

of fact, *zıll* “degradation, a low estate; submissiveness” is a Sufi requirement.⁶⁹ And it is known that ‘İffet was interested in the Nakshbendi and the Mevlevi orders of mysticism. He was even the novice of one of the greater elders of the Nakshbendi, Behcet ‘Alî Efendi, who spent some time in Bursa.⁷⁰ There are some references and intimations in Bursalı İffet’s *divân* that make one surmise he had some inclination to the ideology of the Sufi order *Melâmetiyye* (Arab. *Malâmatiyya*), the members of which place no importance on external elements like clothing or on outwardly following the religious rules. They also pay no attention to public reproach (*melâm*, “a blaming, censuring; blame, censure”) but try to excel in inner sincerity.⁷¹ According to Ethem Cebecioğlu there were dervishes in every Sufi order who preferred the *melâmî* attitude and style (*melâmîlik* or *melâmiyye*).⁷²

Quite the contrary of *tezellül* is found in his following *ğazel*. Here there is a demonstration of personal opinions, of pride, in fact of a total lack of humility. This speaks against a tendency to *melâmiyye*. However, as this is an emulative poem, the original poem that was his “model” would probably play a role in its composition. The model poem is by his contemporary Sheykh Meḥmed Emîn with the pen name Zâ’ik (d. 1852-53);⁷³ unfortunately, we could not compare it with ‘İffet’s poem.

‘İffet, *ğazel* 77, *fe‘ilâtün (fâ‘ilâtün) - fe‘ilâtün - fe‘ilâtün - fe‘ilün (fa‘lün)*

- 1 *Kâse-i Beç’de haṭâ çîn şadâsın çekemem*
Câm-ı ikbâl ile bed-mestüñ edâsın çekemem
- 2 *Olsalar cümle dirim zülfüne gerden-beste*
Böyle bî-kayd cihânuñ budalâsın çekemem
- 3 *Düşmen-i ehl-i sülhan şûfi-i ef’î-nigehüñ*
Beni şâyân-ı bihişt itse riyâsın çekemem

69 See Arzu Eylül Yalçınkaya, “Ahmed er-Rifâi’nin Tasavvuf Anlayışının Anahtar Kavramları: Tevâzu, Meskenet, Züll, İnkisâr, Acz, Fakr,” *Tasavvuf Araştırmaları Enstitüsü Dergisi=Journal of the Institute for Sufi Studies* 1, no. 1 (May 2022): 93-112.

70 Bursalı İffet *Divanı*, 8.

71 Cebecioğlu, “Melâmetiyye,” *Tasavvuf Terimleri ve Deyimleri Sözlüğü*, 498.

72 Cebecioğlu, “Melâmîlik” and “Melâmiyye,” *Tasavvuf Terimleri ve Deyimleri Sözlüğü*, 498-99.

73 Mehmet Gürbüz, “Zâ’ik, Şeyh Meḥmed Emîn Efendi,” *Türk Edebiyatı İsimler Sözlüğü*, <https://teis.yesevi.edu.tr/madde-detay/zaik-seyh-mehmed-emin-efendi> (accessed 17 February 2025).

- 4 *Şu 'arâ-yı selefê hâşılı taklîd⁷⁴ itmem*
Tâb-ı meh-tâbdaki şem'a ziyâsın çekemem
- 5 *Bî-medâr olduğımı nüh-sadefin fehm ideli*
Ben sipihrüñ dañi bihûde-nümâsın çekemem
- 6 *'İffetâ Zâ'ik-i şîrîn-feme 'arz it yoksa*
Nâ-şinâs-ı sühanuñ çân ü çerâsın çekemem⁷⁵
- 1 I can't bear a fault in a bowl from Vienna, a chinking sound.
I can't bear the manner of those who are drunk with the cup of success.
- 2 I say, even if they were all fastened to your tresses by the neck,
I couldn't bear the fools of this universe devoid of restraint.
- 3 Even if he made me fit for heaven, I couldn't bear the hypocrisy
of the Sufi, that eloquent people's foe with the glance of a viper.
- 4 In short, I do not imitate the ancestral poets.
I can't bear the wax taper's light in the radiance of moonlight.
- 5 Since I understood that the nine heavens are no help,
I can't bear even the sky's futile guidance.
- 6 O 'İffet! Present this to sweet-mouthed Zâ'ik. Otherwise
I couldn't bear the grumbling of the ineloquent.

In contrast, 'İffet demonstrates individuality, great self-confidence, and a very good opinion of himself in the next poem.

'İffet, *ğazel* 78, *mefâ'ilün - mefâ'ilün - mefâ'ilün - mefâ'ilün*

- 1 *Leb-i dilber-mizâcım bâde-i minnet kabûl itmem*
Dilim hem-şive-i sîmâb olur nahvet kabûl itmem
- 2 *Mukayyed olmazam derd-i humâr-ı câm-ı takdîre*
Naşîhat gûş kılmam nükte-i hikmet kabûl itmem
- 3 *Bakılrsa kâbil-i her şüretim ammâ perîşânım*
Şikest âyîneyim gûyâ ki bir şüret kabûl itmem
- 4 *Yazıklar baña bunda zevk-i dîger hâsil itmezsem*
Virilse böyle bî-'irfân iken cennet kabûl itmem

74 The object of the verb *taqlîd et-* ("to imitate") takes the dative instead of the accusative here and in the following verse 78/5.

75 *Bursalı İffet Dîvânı*, 78-79.

- 5 *Egerçi sâde-nazmım ‘İffetâ âşâr-ı tab‘ımdır
Kelâm-ı ğayre taklîd eylemem sirikat kabûl itmem*⁷⁶
- 1 The darling’s lips are to my taste, I refuse the wine of favour.
And my heart is timid mannered, I do not accept conceit.
- 2 I am not made drunk with the cup of appreciation.
I do not listen to advice. I do not accept wise sayings.
- 3 If one considers, I am capable of any form. But I am disordered.
I am a broken mirror; it is as though I accept no form.
- 4 Woe is me if I don’t produce some other pleasure here.
Were paradise to be given me while so ignorant, I wouldn’t accept.
- 5 O ‘İffet, though my simple poems are the products of my nature,
I do not imitate the words of others. I do not accept plagiarism.

Conclusion

Based on the poems, mainly *ġazels*, of Bākī and Me’ālī in the 16th century, and of those of Hızırġazāde Sa’īd and ‘İffet of Bursa in the 19th century, we suggest that the moderate style of wit of the old school of Ottoman poetry was most probably still popular in the first half of the 19th century in as far as the zealot (*zāhid*), the Sufī, and the *sofu* were concerned. Over time, these had evolved into *types*, though they were not as complex characters as, for example, the *types* of the Turkish shadow theatre. As the words *şūfī* and *sofu* are both spelled *şūfī* in *Dīvān* poetry, the reader must decide whether the poet means *şūfī*, the nonconformist mystic who has a positive image in high-culture *Dīvān* poetry, or if he means *sofu*, who resembles the *zāhid* in his overzealous adherence to religious tenets and is suspected of insincerity, so that he has a negative image in this poetry, as does the *zāhid*.

In at least one instance in the 19th century, that of the poet ‘İffet of Bursa, humorous self-deprecation ceases to be light-hearted as seen, for example, in Me’ālī’s verses on his physique in the 16th century. Serious self-deprecation is probably linked to mystic (*taşavvuf*) requirements regarding humility. Intriguingly, extreme humility alternates with exaggerated self-praise, though not in the same poem.

⁷⁶ *Bursalı İffet Dīvānı*, 79.

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